

The Meaning of the Common Consolidates Corporate Tax Base in the Republic of Croatia

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Abstract

As of 1 July 2013, i.e. upon Croatian accession to the European Union, the European Union will consist of 28 member states. Diversity of tax systems among member states causes interferences in cross-border activities of tax firms. That encourages transfer of income to countries with lower tax rates. The aim of this paper is to present the main points of view on implications of the introduction of the Common Consolidates Corporate Tax Base (CCCTB) in Croatia. This paper also estimates the effects of prospective apportionment procedure on corporate group entity in Croatia.

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Keywords: Corporate income taxation, tax revenue, formula apportionment, Croatia

1. Introduction

In November 2004 European Commission has established Working Group responsible for setting up the basic standards and structure of the CCCTB. The main objectives of the CCCTB Working Group were to discuss about principles that will govern the CCCTB, to examine the technical definition of a common consolidated tax base for companies in more than one member state, to establish fundamental structural elements of a consolidated tax base and to formulate a mechanism for the allocation of the consolidates tax base between different member states. Proposal of the CCCTB aims to enable a simplified tax system for companies. It would reduce tax compliance costs and remove the existing tax obstacles that companies face when they operate in several member states.

The CCCTB is a system of common rules for computing the tax base of companies which are tax residents in the EU and in the EU-located branches of the third country companies (COM, 2011, p. 121). A central feature of the CCCTB is cross-border consolidation and setting up a single rule that companies operating within the EU could use to calculate their taxable profits. The CCCTB regime ensures cross-border gain and loss offset and reduces operating costs in the long run. All of the above can be achieved through formula apportionment. The key benefit of the implementation of formula apportionment method among the tax system of the EU's member states is the avoidance of double taxation and the prevention of income shifting. The main aim of its introduction is to establish tax profits and losses of international companies that have subsidiaries in different member states. It would offer a possibility to cover profits and losses in order to reach common result of operations among companies. The overall taxable income, calculated in such manner, would be assigned to individual member states by sharing mechanism. The introduction of a new consolidation and apportionment system would have two effects (Devereux and Loretz, 2007, p. 2). First, loss-making companies could benefit from international loss consolidation to the extent which they could offset losses against contemporaneous profits made by other companies within the same group in other countries. Second, the effects of the apportionment of group taxable profit to specific member states depends on where the profit is allocated and the set of tax rates consequently applied.

Further on, the main aim of the paper will be explained, and the manner how formula apportionment impacts income distribution and tax burden will be succinctly discussed. Furthermore, advantages and disadvantages of the

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CCCTB and some basic principles of the CCCTB will be presented, as well as the implementation of the CCCTB in Croatia.

2. Advantages and disadvantages of the CCCTB

Introduction of the CCCTB would compensate trans-border income among the member states. Such income tax base emphasizes economic benefits because consolidated companies could use their overall economic potential in both Croatia or any other member state. By applying CCCTB, profit or loss realised by funds transfers within a group is postponed until it is realized on the real market. Costs and corresponding revenues from transactions are then calculated within the group on the market. After the introduction of this model in all member states expected benefits would include (COM, 2001, p. 16):

1. significant reduction of compliance costs
2. disappearance of the double taxation problem within the EU
3. removing a major obstacle to the free movement of capital and unrestricted exercise of the right of establishment, by cross-border loss compensation of tax losses by reducing the taxable profits of parent companies
4. disappearance of the tax avoidance practices by using transfer pricing, because inter-firm transaction prices can not affect the distribution of taxable income to tax jurisdictions
5. comparability of effective tax burdens in each jurisdiction with the result of an improvement in the quality of investment and hence of resource allocation to the whole EU

European Commission and the CCCTB system representatives are certain that the new system will offer numerous advantages to both international company and overall European economy. Such advantages include decrease in the expenses of harmonization and simplification of procedures, possibility to consolidate company's incomes and losses in community, increased transparency, decrease of tax uncertainty and increase in economic efficiency, elimination of discrimination, elimination of double taxation and prevention of non-taxation and misuse. The EU, as a whole, will benefit the most from consolidation when the system becomes compulsory and the tax rates harmonised (Horst, Bettendorf and Rojas-Romagosa, 2007, p. 31).

Commission's decision to stand up for the introduction of the CCCTB system is based upon the assumption that in the example of the common tax base advantages of such system take into consideration its weaknesses as well. Potentially negative consequences include loss of national tax systems, loss of fiscal policy instruments for regulation of relations on the national market, reduction of the system advantages due to problems of the taxation of incomes that European companies make outside the EU and decrease of budget revenues from corporate taxation. If all countries join the CCCTB reform, this benefit will be partly offset by two possible negative effects (Bettendorf, Van der Horst, De Mooij and Vrijburg, 2010, p. 475). The first is due to the mechanical reallocation of the tax base, which depends on the choice of the formula. The second is induced by the factor reallocation towards low-tax countries. High-tax countries suffer from an outflow of production factors by multinationals towards low-tax countries because corporate tax rates work as excises on the formula factors. Under common consolidated base taxation, all or a group of Member States would agree on a set of common rules for establishing the taxable base of certain enterprises (Weiner, 2002, p. 521).

2.1. Principles of the CCCTB

CCCTB must provide a comprehensive and autonomous set of rules. According to Freedman and Macdonald (2007) the role of principles should be twofold (p. 7). From one point of view, they should provide both a reference point for determining the scope of the tax base through a legislative statement of the central concept which encompasses the substantive nature of the tax base. From another point of view, constitutionally valid framework is the form of criteria for interpreting and applying the provisions of Directive.

The principles are essentially normative standards applied in designing tax system of each country. The common principles of the CCCTB are in line with the general principles of tax system. These principles are vertical and horizontal equity, efficiency, effectiveness, simplicity, transparency and certainty, consistency and coherence, flexibility and enforceability.

In a tax system, the vertical equity principle implies that the burden of taxation should be shared in accordance with taxpayers' respective ability to pay. In horizontal equity, taxpayers in the same economic circumstances should receive equivalent treatment. An EU CCCTB would aim to provide equity between countries as part of the consolidation process and the subsequent sharing of the tax base between countries (European Commission, 2004, p. 4)). Capital Export Neutrality (CEN) and Capital Import Neutrality (CIN) are concept which aim is to ensure neutrality (European Commission, 2004, p. 4). Vital elements of tax systems are principles of effectiveness, simplicity, transparency and certainty, consistency, flexibility and enforceability. Effectiveness is essentially the capacity of the tax base to achieve its basic objectives. The principles must also be certain and clear, relating to the requirement for transparency. Tax base principle must be easy to enforce since an unenforceable system is unlikely to be either equitable or neutral. General principles are viewed from a national perspective so that the CCCTB Working Group still needs to clarify in detail how these principles will be considered in a definitive or final way.

3. The EU formula apportionment

According to Fuest, Hemmelgarn and Ramb (2006), the revenue effects of the introduction of formula apportionment discussion in the EU include a system of cross-border loss relief (p. 20). They also find expected decrease in the tax revenues of the EU member states. The choice of the apportionment formula is important for two reasons (Bettendorf, Van der Horst, De Mooij and Vrijburg, 2010, p. 454). First, the formula determines the distribution of the tax base across jurisdictions. Second, formula apportionment imposes an implicit excise tax on the apportionment factor. Companies can influence their corporate tax liability by locating the factors that enter the formula in low-tax jurisdictions. As long as tax rates differ across jurisdictions, the allocation of investment and employment will be influenced under formula apportionment. Corporate income taxation is based on a consolidated tax base, and tax revenues are apportioned among countries according to formula (Pethig and Wagener, 2007, p. 633). Under formula apportionment, a multinational would report its EU-wide taxable income to every EU country in which it is active and this income would be allocated among each EU country for tax purposes based on a formula that could use a variety of relative cost and revenue ratios (Gresik, 2010, p. 134). A multinational firm's global income would be assigned to countries by a formula based on the fraction of their worldwide activity that occurred in each country (Clausing and Lahav, 2011, p. 99).

Under this taxation system, international companies would be allowed to cover their losses on the EU level. Incomes and losses of one group of companies would not be separated by countries in which certain dependant companies from a group are located. Instead, all taxable losses and incomes would be consolidated at the beginning. By doing so, spillover among particular companies from a group would become pointless. The taxable profit would be firstly dictated according to common rules. All parts of the group would be consolidated and the group profit would be allocated by formula apportionment to different member states. Corporate tax rate would be agreed upon according to the single taxing system. The apportionment formula includes three factors. These factors are Sales (S), Labour (L) and Assets (A). Labour factor is divided into two factors. These factors are payroll of the work force and number of employees. According to the Article 86 (COM, 2011, p. 47) the apportionment formula:

$$\text{Share A} = \left[\frac{1}{3} \times \frac{\text{Sales}^A}{\text{Sales}_{\text{Group}}} + \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\text{Payroll}^A}{\text{Payroll}_{\text{Group}}} + \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\text{Employees}^A}{\text{Employees}_{\text{Group}}} \right) + \frac{1}{3} \times \frac{\text{Assets}^A}{\text{Assets}_{\text{Group}}} \right] \times \text{CTB} \quad (1)$$

with CTB representing the consolidated overall results of the group.

Equation (1) shows system according to which distributed tax base would be located in different member states.

The choice of the apportionment factors of a formula should follow the objectives according to which the formula should (CCCTB, sharing):

1. be as simple as possible to apply for taxpayers and tax administrations and easy to audit for tax administrations
2. be difficult to manipulate by the taxpayers
3. be considered to lead to a fair and equitable distribution of the tax bases among the various entities concerned
4. not lead to undesirable effects in terms of tax competition.

The apportionment formula can only allocate a share of the consolidated group income to the group entity that equals the group entity's pre-consolidation income if all used apportionment factors are uniformly distributed between the group entity and the corporate group (Petutsching, 2010, p. 23).

As soon as Croatia joins the EU, each member state will have the right to tax the allocated share of the consolidated tax base applying its own national corporate tax base.

Example 1.

A multinational company consists of Company A and Company B. Company A resides and sells its output in Croatia, and Company B resides and sells its output in Slovenia. Information about sales, payroll, employees and assets for both countries are provided in Table 1. Corporate income tax rate for Slovenia in 2013 is 17% and for Croatia is 20%.

Table 1. Example of the formula apportionment application

Companies	Sales	Payroll and Employees	Assets	Taxable Income
Croatia (Company A)	50	50	50	40
Slovenia (Company B)	70	30	30	50
Total	120	80	80	

Source: Author's calculation

Considering the above information, tax burden under separate accounting per company and the total tax burden for the group amounts to 16.5.

$$T_A = 40 \times 0.2 = 8 \quad T_B = 50 \times 0.17 = 8.5 \quad T = T_A + T_B = 16.5$$

Applying the apportionment formula according to Article 86 and assuming an identical tax base, the tax burden per company and the total tax burden for the group amounts to 17.1.

$$T_A = 0.2 \times (40 + 50) \times \left(\frac{1}{3} \times \frac{50}{120} + \frac{1}{3} \times \frac{50}{80} + \frac{1}{3} \times \frac{50}{80} \right) = 10,1$$

$$T_B = 0.17 \times (40 + 50) \times \left(\frac{1}{3} \times \frac{70}{120} + \frac{1}{3} \times \frac{30}{80} + \frac{1}{3} \times \frac{30}{80} \right) = 7$$

$$T = T_A + T_B = 17.1$$

Example 1 shows that formula apportionment would significantly change total tax burden for groups of companies. It may also provide incentives to increase tax competition. Increasing tax competition under the proposed CCCTB may encourage member states to further decrease tax rates on corporate profits (Spengel and Zöllkau, 2012, p. 14). According to this example, it can be concluded that member states with higher income tax rate have higher total tax burden. That is one of the factors that adversely affects multinational companies' decision to locate their enterprises in those countries. By comparing companies in Croatia and Italy, it can be concluded that it is easy for multinational companies to do business in Italy because their tax burden is lower. Lower tax burden allows companies to earn more. Besides, they become more attractive to foreign investors.

4. Implementation of the CCCTB into Croatia

All rules on the CCCTB system should be implemented in the Republic of Croatia upon its accession to the European Union on 01 July 2013. Application of the common consolidated corporate tax base would reduce tax compliance costs. By applying formula apportionment such consolidated tax base would be distributed among member states. By applying the concept of consolidation, multinational companies that do business in several member countries would have to calculate taxes according to only one tax systems. Use of consolidated base would mean that the profit and loss of the entire multinational company are accumulated to a simple general tax base. Thus, there would be no more need for transfer pricing and international double taxation would disappear. By accepting consolidated base within income tax, multinational companies should be allowed to calculate overall income by applying common regulations.

The expected results of the application of the CCCTB are as follows (COM, 2011, p.15):

1. to allow cross-border loss-offset
2. to reduce occurrences of double or over-taxation
3. to reduce undue or unintended tax planning opportunities for companies by the parallel application of 27 corporate tax system in the EU
4. to introduce a one-stop shop approach for tax declarations and assessment
5. to provide companies with the option to apply a common system for taxation in the EU
6. to reduce transfer pricing compliance obligations

Should Croatia decide to implement the CCCTB, it will have a choice of implementing it as its individual tax base or as a tax base that is alternative to the existing one. Furthermore, replacement of Croatian corporate income tax base with the CCCTB would cause numerous transitional problems of moving from the existing tax base to the CCCTB for both Croatian entities and entities moving between the two systems. Domestic tax incentives would no longer be on the market to firms because they are not deductible under the CCCTB system. Likewise, issues on whether Croatia adopts the CCCTB as its only tax base or as an additional tax base have been raised.

The probability of Croatia implementing the CCCTB as its individual tax base is very limited. More realistic situation would be the one in which the CCCTB exists side by side with the national tax base. It should be noted that the two tax bases would effectively compete with each other. For example, if a loss-making group company wants to sell assets transferred to its intra-group to a person outside of the group, it may choose the CCCTB regime pursuant to which there is a fleeting holding period for the intra-group transfer to remain exempt. Similarly, if a group company wants to sell its major shareholding in another group company, it might choose to do so under the CCCTB regime. There is no requirement for the selling company to be a business company. If Croatia does not implement the CCCTB, at least as an alternative tax base, the CCCTB will be treated as just another foreign tax base. From a Croatian point of view, inbound and outbound investments in the CCCTB area would be taxed in the same way as investment in any other foreign jurisdiction. That would be very confusing and economically unacceptable to foreign investors. From a CCCTB point of view, the rules on the taxation of inbound and outbound investment are somewhat different from the conventional single country rules. Croatia can be affected in unanticipated ways. To that extent, these rules require special attention.

5. Conclusion

Current situation in the area of corporate taxation in the EU is characterized by diverse tax systems, great differences in tax burden on companies in particular member states and strong tax competition. For individual member states, the benefits from consolidation and formula apportionment are diverse and depend on the formula choice. The formula defines the distribution of the corporate tax base across the EU countries and, thereby, the revenue implications of the reform.

Upon accession to the European Union on 01 July, Croatia will become a full member. It will become 28th member state of the European Union. That means that the area of European Union will comprise 28 different tax systems. Diversity of income taxation systems within the European Union causes interferences in cross-border business of multinational companies. Thus, it encourages shifting income to member states with lower income tax rates in order to accumulate more profit. Besides adverse effect on economic growth and economy of the country, it will also influence the European Union as a consolidated market. In order to eliminate these problems, the European Union has taken precautionary measures. Establishing the CCCTB system is one of the measures. Implementation of such system in the member states will present major challenges for the business sector. That will be a major challenge for Croatia as well since further modification of its tax system will be demanded. As a result, the Income Tax Act will be modified and companies will have to adjust to it. Acceptance CCCTB system will make Croatia attractive to foreign investors. It will enable foreign multinational companies to do business in Croatia as well, which will contribute to its economic growth. As soon as Croatia joins the EU, each member state will have to compare their own tax base with the CCCTB to see if abstinence from implementation of the CCCTB will be at their disadvantage and/or if the two bases can co-exist without eroding each other.

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